

Article

Advanced Methods for Monitoring and Fault Diagnosis of Control Loops in Common Rail Systems

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Abstract: Common rail systems are a key component of modern diesel engines and highly increase their performance. During their working lifetime, there could be critical damages or failures related to aging, like backlash or friction, or out-of-spec operating conditions, like low-quality fuel with, e.g., the presence of water or particles or a high percentage of biodiesel. In this work, suitable data-driven methods are adopted to develop an automatic procedure to monitor, diagnose, and estimate some types of faults in common rail systems. In particular, the pressure control loop operating within the engine control unit is investigated; the system is described using a Hammerstein model composed of a nonlinear model for the control valve behavior and an extended linear model for the process dynamics, which also accounts for the presence of external disturbances. Three different sources of oscillations can be successfully detected and quantified: valve stiction, aggressive controller tuning, and external disturbance. Selected case studies are used to demonstrate the effectiveness of the developed methodology.

Keywords: condition monitoring; fault detection and diagnosis; common rail system; pressure control; valve stiction; system identification

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1. Introduction

The diesel common rail system has revolutionized fuel injection in diesel engines, offering numerous advantages such as improved fuel efficiency, reduced emissions, and precise control over fuel delivery [1]. This technology has become the standard in modern diesel engines, providing higher performance and lower environmental impact.

In particular, the high-pressure rail of the common rail system allows precise fuel injections with minor waste and thus reduces noise and polluting emissions. This device binds the pump and injectors together as the central hydraulic component, stores the compressed fuel, and supplies it to the injectors; a rail pressure sensor and—independent of the system configuration—an additional pressure control valve or pressure limiting valve is typically fitted on the high-pressure rail as rail-assembled components. Over 60,000 pressure checks per minute are performed to regulate the fuel injection [2].

However, the complexity of the common rail system presents challenges in diagnosing and maintaining optimal pressure control, which is essential for its efficient operation. To this aim, interesting works of modeling, monitoring, diagnosis, and control applied to common rail systems are present in the literature.

For example, a comprehensive analysis of ball check valves with conical and spherical seat designs in common rail pumps was performed in [3]. An experimental investigation of the combustion process and the injection strategy of a heavy-duty diesel engine equipped with common rail fuel injection system was performed in [4]. The strategies for achieving the ideal compromise between fuel economy and tailpipe emissions are discussed and presented therein. Another experimental study on the effect of post-injection parameters on performance of extra-high pressure common rail diesel engine was conducted by [5]. Moreover, the effect of fuel injection pressure on organic carbon, elemental carbon, and

particulate semi-volatile organic compounds emissions, i.e., n-alkanes and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, prove to play a major role in the performance control of high-pressure common rail (HPCR) [6].

A recent study on precise fuel injection under multiple injections in HPCR systems based on a deep learning model with generalized regression neural networks was conducted by [7]; particle swarm optimization was then introduced to optimize the smoothing factor in the model. In [8], a real-time estimation method for the injection rate and volume based on the measurable rail pressure is derived by considering both the effect of fuel injection and supply process on the pressure fluctuation and a linear time-varying state space model is constructed by choosing three appropriate state variables. Moreover, a real-time estimation method of the fuel mass injected in large injections in common rail diesel engines based on system identification using an artificial neural network was presented by [9].

In [10], the design and application of a model-free controller with an algebraic estimator and ultra-local model on the HPCR in a direct injection fuel system of an internal combustion engine was presented. Finally, the rail pressure tracking problem of an HPCR system is investigated using a generalized proportional integral observer (GPIO)-based composite control algorithm [11].

Among possible problems of the common rail system, sustained oscillations of the control variable, that is, the rail pressure, are typically observed. Oscillations can arise because of pressure control itself or because of external oscillating sources interacting with this control variable. Such undesired behavior can highly affect the performance of the common rail system and may degrade the operation of the whole diesel engine, thus reducing generated traction power and combustion performance and then augmenting final emissions. In addition to external disturbances and tight controller tuning, the proportional valve used for the pressure control may exhibit non-negligible static and dynamic friction, which typically occurs due to natural system aging. Valve stiction generates persistent oscillations due to the cyclic conflict with the feedback controller, which tries to force the rail pressure to its setpoint; the controller output indeed varies while the valve position is blocked due to friction. When the control action overcomes friction, the valve moves abruptly, so an overshoot in the control variable occurs. Therefore, it is crucial to adopt efficient methods for oscillation detection and diagnosis and hence discriminate between different sources of malfunctions that may have similar effects on the registered data [12]. To this aim, the valve position, as a measured or at least estimated variable, reveals the key signal to assess the correct source of the fault [13].

This paper responds to the need for a fully automated methodology for monitoring, detecting, and diagnosing different sources of malfunction that occur within common rail systems. The proposed approach is based on well-established methods of the literature for performance monitoring and diagnosis of control loops within the process industry. As a novelty, according to the best authors' knowledge, this work is the first example of an automated procedure of detection and estimation of common faults, such as valve stiction, external disturbance, and controller tuning, for control loops of common rail systems.

The remainder of the paper is as follows. Section 2 describes the proposed methodology: the system is described using a Hammerstein model composed of a nonlinear model for the control valve and an extended input/output linear model for the controlled process, which also accounts for external disturbances. Selected case studies are presented and discussed in Section 3 to demonstrate the effectiveness of the developed methodology in detecting and quantifying three different sources of oscillations: valve stiction, aggressive controller tuning, and external disturbance. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section 4.

2. Materials and Methods

The developed automatic methodology for the monitoring and fault diagnosis of control loops in common rail systems is detailed as follows.

2.1. The Considered System

The simplified common rail system under investigation is shown in Figure 1. The Engine Control Unit (ECU) operates as the main control element by managing two different control variables, the engine speed and the rail system pressure. The first output of the ECU sets the injector current for the engine speed control, while the second output operates the current for the Metering Unit (MeUn), that is, the proportional electric valve, for the rail pressure control. This valve indeed regulates the pressure of the High Pressure Pump (HPP), which then pushes diesel fuel in the form of micro-drops through the common rail system into the set of injectors and then into the engine cylinders.

In the following study, we consider the single-input single-output (SISO) pressure control loop operating in feedback which comprises three dynamic elements: the ECU as a Proportional–Integral–Derivative (PID) controller, the MeUn as the actuator device, and the rail system as the process to be controlled. Therefore, the speed control loop is outside of the considered system boundaries.

The corresponding variables used for the following analyses are as follows: the rail pressure set-point (SP) expressed in bar; the rail pressure measurement as the control variable (PV) in bar; the current of MeUn as the controller output (OP) in mA. The actual manipulated variable (MV) lies indeed within the MeUn, and is related to the actual valve position expressed in mm or % of the valve span. This variable is not measured online and must instead be estimated by the other loop signals for the aforementioned monitoring and diagnosis purposes. Note that, when the valve characteristic is known, the controller output (OP) as a current can be converted directly into the valve position demand (in %). The engine speed measurement (in rpm) is here assumed as an external disturbance entering the HPP; finally, additional process disturbances coming from the other vehicle subsystems may affect the common rail system.

Figure 1. Simplified block diagram of the common rail system under investigation.

2.2. The Dynamic Model

An extended Hammerstein model is adopted as a framework for the system dynamics description and the corresponding analysis of the root causes of oscillation. This two-block nonlinear model is formed of a preliminary dynamic nonlinear block, which involves the proportional valve of the Metering Unit, and a subsequent linear block for the process dynamics, which is the time evolution of the controlled system, comprised of the high-pressure pump (HPP) and rail system (see Figure 1).

In particular, an Extended AutoRegressive–Moving-Average with eXogenous input (EARMAX) model, which was first introduced by [14], is here exploited for the process dynamics, that is, for describing the rail pressure as the control variable (PV). The adopted linear equation in time-series form is as follows:

$$y_k + a_1 y_{k-1} + \dots + a_{n_a} y_{k-n_a} = b_1 x_{k-\tau-1} + \dots + b_{n_b} x_{k-\tau-n_b} + e_k + c_1 e_{k-1} + \dots + c_{n_c} e_{k-n_c} + \eta_k \quad (1)$$

where the subscript k denotes the k -th time sample; n_a is the order of output signal ($y = PV$), with a_j its j -th coefficient; n_b is the order of the input signal (x), that is, the valve output (MV), with b_j its j -th coefficient, and τ is the corresponding time-delay; n_c is the error model order, and c_j its j -th coefficient; finally, η_k is a time-varying input that acts as an external disturbance and extends the traditional ARMAX model. Alternative linear model structures, in input/output or state-space form, such as the ones available in our open-source tool for system identification [15], could be used, but we here limit to the EARMAX model for the sake of brevity, since this structure is highly flexible and proves efficient in describing such complex dynamic systems.

The valve dynamics, which may be affected by static friction, is described by using the well-established data-driven Kano model [16]. This practical nonlinear model is only based on two main empirical parameters: the sum of stick-band and dead-band (S), and the stick-slip jump (J) (see Figure 2). Note that $S = f_s + f_d$ and $J = f_s - f_d$, f_s and f_d being the static and dynamic friction, respectively. Valve stiction generates a typical parallelogram-shape limit cycle that appears from visual inspection of the paths registered on the polar graph between the valve position demand, that is, the controller output ($u = OP$), and the actual valve position, that is, the manipulated variable ($x = MV$). As said, the MV signal is not usually measured, so the polar plot MV(OP) is not known; therefore, detection and diagnosis methods have to rely only on the two available variables, OP and PV.

Figure 2. (Left) flow diagram of the Kano stiction model, adapted from [16]. (Right) theoretical limit cycle produced by the valve stiction on the polar graph MV(OP) [17].

Note that this model was originally developed for the pneumatic control valves of industrial process plants, but it has been successfully applied to electric valves and different types of actuators, as demonstrated by [18,19]. Periodic oscillation and cyclic paths typical of friction have been indeed registered for the electric valves installed in the common rail systems, as shown by the case study of Section 3.

In the adopted detection and diagnosis methodology, the controller tuning is also verified to monitor the control system performance and discriminate between different sources of malfunctions. To this aim, since the parameters of the pressure controller within the ECU are initially set by the device producer and are not available to the final user, they

are here estimated from the registered data as suggested by [20]. The standard equation for the PID controller in velocity form and the discrete-time domain is adopted, as follows:

$$u_k - u_{k-1} = K_P(\epsilon_k - \epsilon_{k-1}) + K_I\epsilon_k + K_D(\epsilon_k - 2\epsilon_{k-1} + \epsilon_{k-2}) \quad (2)$$

where u is the controller output (OP), that is, the valve position demand, and $\epsilon = r - y$ is the control error, that is, the difference between the set-point (r) and process variable (y); while K_P , K_I , and K_D are the PID controller proportional, integral, and derivative gain.

Once the various dynamic blocks (that is, the controller, valve, and process) are evaluated, a classic closed-loop analysis is performed to simulate the whole pressure control loop of the common rail system as shown in Figure 1.

2.3. The Algorithm Steps

The automatic algorithm proposed for the monitoring and fault diagnosis of common rail systems is implemented in MATLAB and involves the following main steps:

1. *Compute the stabilization time of the valve stiction model of Kano.*
As previously evidenced by [17] (see Figure 4 therein), to properly employ the Kano stiction model, the ambiguity in the initialization of the three auxiliary parameters (u_s, stp, d) must be solved, since different initializations produce different trends of valve position in the transient period. Therefore, the corresponding stabilization time, for which the effect of a specific initialization has expired, is evaluated.
2. *Estimate Hammerstein model parameters over the linear orders and S/J grid.*
For each node of the external grid of the two stiction parameters (S/J), all the possible combinations in the selected set of process model orders are tested. The orders of the linear process, that is, the EARMAX model (n_a, n_b, n_c), are indeed evaluated by using an internal grid-search method within a predefined range, e.g., $n_a \in [n_a^{min}, n_a^{max}]$. Note that the stiction grid has a triangular shape: $S \geq J$ by definition since the cases of the so-called "overshoot" stiction are excluded; the maximum tested value of stiction is related to the valve input variation range, that is, $\max(S) = \Delta u$. Four approaches are adopted for the selection of the best EARMAX model orders: the statistical test of [21] and three well-established information criteria (Akaike, corrected Akaike, and Bayesian). Then, a weighted scoring system of the Borda count type is used to merge the results of the four aforementioned tests [22]. Finally, process input–output time-delay τ is estimated by using the cross-correlation function `xcorr` of MATLAB between the valve output (x , that is, MV) and the control variable (y , that is, PV).
3. *Evaluate the best combination of the EARMAX and Kano models.*
The solution of the adopted two-level grid-search method is given by the combination of process and stiction parameters that minimize the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the actual output (y) and the Hammerstein model output (\hat{y}), defined as follows:

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{k=0}^{N_s-1} (y_k - \hat{y}_k)^2 \quad (3)$$

where N_s is the number of samples, and $\hat{y} = \hat{y}_m + \hat{\eta}$ is the sum of the estimated undisturbed output (\hat{y}_m) and the estimated time-varying external disturbance ($\hat{\eta}$). The optimal solution is given by (\hat{S}, \hat{J}) for the stiction parameters and $\hat{\theta}$ for the linear process parameters. The corresponding process transfer function $P(z)$ is evaluated, z being the time-shift operator.

4. *Estimate the PID controller parameters.*
The PID controller parameters are estimated using Equation (2). The controller transfer function $C(z)$ is then calculated, and the corresponding closed-loop transfer function $\zeta(z) = \frac{PC}{1+PC}$ is obtained. Note that a two-stage approach is used: (i) firstly, a standard linear least-squares (LLS) method is used; (ii) secondly, a constrained optimization-based method is adopted in the case of closed-loop instability. In particular, the standard `fmincon` function of MATLAB is exploited.

5. Evaluate the oscillation features of periodic signals.

The features of oscillation of the loop signals, that is, the process variable y , the time-varying disturbance η , and the closed-loop response ζ are evaluated by using the corresponding sample auto-correlation function (ACF). In particular, two well-established indices are computed: (i) the regularity factor r [23], defined as

$$r = \frac{1}{3} \frac{\bar{T}_p}{\sigma_{T_p}} \quad (4)$$

where \bar{T}_p is the average period of oscillation, evaluated as the mean zero-crossings period, and σ_{T_p} is the standard deviation of the period; (ii) the decay ratio R_{acf} [24], evaluated as

$$R_{acf} = \frac{a}{b} \quad (5)$$

where a is the distance from the first maximum to the straight line connecting the first two minima of ACF, and b is the distance from the first minimum to the straight line that connects the zero-lag auto-covariance coefficient and the first maximum (see Figure 3). Note that the sample ACF is still oscillatory if the original signal is oscillatory, but ACF has the major property of filtering out the detrimental effect of field noise. Oscillatory signals with $r > 1.0$ and $R_{acf} > 0.5$ are considered regular and persistent, respectively; in other words, the corresponding source of oscillation is significant.

Figure 3. Auto-correlation function (ACF) of an example oscillatory signal.

3. Case Studies and Results Discussion

The developed methodology is now applied to two significant datasets of malfunction. The presented examples were selected to demonstrate the wide applicability and relative effectiveness of the proposed methodology. The two case studies are related to a test bench of a complete diesel engine of a medium-sized passenger car owned by an Italian company. The considered setup includes the pressure control loop of the common rail system depicted in Figure 1. Note that the true causes of faults and corresponding sources of sustained oscillation are known a priori. Data are extracted with a sampling time of 1 s and then normalized for privacy reasons to zero mean and unitary standard deviation.

The following parameters were adopted: the EARMAX model orders are searched in the range $n_a, n_b, n_c \in [1, 3]$, and the same weight is assigned to the four statistical tests for selecting the best orders; the stiction grid S/J comprises 30 nodes per side.

3.1. Case 1

This first case study refers to a known scenario of medium-level stiction affecting the electric valve installed within the Metering Unit of the common rail system. The full

methodology of Section 2.3 is applied, and the corresponding results are summarized in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Case 1: medium-level stiction scenario.

All the control loop signals are affected by significant periodic oscillations. The overall diagnosis proves to be correct since valve stiction is detected by the proposed methodology. The identified stiction parameters are $S = J = 2.45$, which corresponds to a medium-severe stiction scenario: the valve is blocked for more than 75% of the controller output excursion, but since $S = J$, it can jump between the two extreme positions (see Subplot (d) of Figure 4). As a consequence, the polar plot MV(OP) shown in Subplot (e) exhibits limit cycles with a close-to-square shape. Nevertheless, an external disturbance and an aggressive tuning in the PI controller are simultaneously affecting the pressure control loop. As shown by Subplot (a), the rail pressure (y) shows a clear triangular-shape wave, which is a typical hint of valve stiction, with a very regular oscillation (regularity $r = 69.73$) and a highly sustained feature (decay ratio $R_{acf} = 0.98$). A non-negligible external time-varying disturbance is also detected, as shown in Subplot (b). This signal has a regular ($r = 6.24$) and sustained ($R_{acf} = 0.54$) oscillation, with a slight increasing drift. Also, the closed-loop response is oscillating, again regular ($r = 6.32$) and sustained ($R_{acf} = 0.92$) (see Subplot (c)). Finally, note that the average periods (in seconds) of three detected sources of oscillation (\bar{T}_p) are different: 82.4 for valve stiction, 27.7 for the disturbance, and 79.8 for the closed-loop response. As an outcome, our approach suggests the engine operators perform valve maintenance and controller retuning.

3.2. Case 2

The second case study refers to a known scenario of high-level stiction in the electric valve with an external disturbance entering the control loop simultaneously. Again the full methodology of Section 2.3 is applied and the corresponding results are summarized in Figure 5.

All the registered signals show significant oscillations; once again, the overall diagnosis appears to be appropriate, as valve stiction is indeed assessed. The identified stiction parameters are $S = 2.66, J = 1.27$ and correspond to a high stiction scenario: the valve is indeed blocked for 70% of the controller output excursion, and since $S > J$, the actual valve position differs significantly from its demand given by the controller. As a consequence, the polar plot MV(OP) shown in Subplot (e) exhibits limit cycles with a clear parallelogram shape. As observed by Subplot (a), the rail pressure (y) exhibits saw-tooth waves, which is another typical hint of valve stiction; the oscillation appears to be asymmetrical, so

it becomes slightly regular ($r = 0.76$) but sustained, since decay ratio $R_{acf} = 0.62$. A large time-varying disturbance is also detected by Subplot (b): this signal has a regular ($r = 8.74$) and sustained ($R_{acf} = 0.57$) oscillation, with a mean value equal to $\bar{\eta} = 0.269$ bar with an amplitude of 0.49 bar, which is particularly significant when related to the rail pressure, whose amplitude is around 3.41 bar. In this case, the closed-loop response is a non-oscillating signal (its R_{acf} is close to zero), a scenario related to a well-tuned PI controller (see Subplot (c)). Valve maintenance and external disturbance mitigation are suggested to the engine operators in this second case.

Figure 5. Case 2: high-level stiction scenario.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, a comprehensive methodology for monitoring and fault detection of control loops in common rail systems is presented. This key device of the diesel engine may suffer from sustained oscillation due to different sources of malfunctions. The pressure control loop of the common rail is investigated and described by using a Hammerstein model composed of a nonlinear data-driven model for the valve behavior and an extended ARMAX model for the linear process dynamics, which also accounts for the presence of external disturbances. Three different sources of oscillations can be automatically detected and quantified: valve stiction, aggressive controller tuning, and external disturbance. As consequent remedies, valve maintenance, controller retuning, and disturbance mitigation are suggested to the engine operators. The flexibility and effectiveness of the developed methodology has been demonstrated by using two selected case studies of a test bench engine. Future developments will focus on building a multivariable model of the common rail system, where both the pressure and speed control loop and the corresponding interactions are considered, and further sources of malfunction are investigated.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

EARMAX	Extended AutoRegressive–Moving-Average with eXogenous input
ECU	Engine Control Unit
HPP	High Pressure Pump
MSE	Mean Squared Error
MU	Metering Unit
OP	Output Process
PID	Proportional-Integral-Derivative
PV	Process Variable
SP	Set-Point

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